

SOCIAL SCIENCES

INTERNET MEDIA AND INFORMATION SECURITY ISSUES IN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The article talks about the goal-oriented work carried out in the direction of the protection of state independence and national interests in cyberspace, the improvement of a unified state policy in the field of information security, and the creation of technological infrastructure components of information security after Azerbaijan gained independence.

Keywords: Information security, cyber security, media, technology.

The policy of achieving freedom of speech and information in Azerbaijan, the formation of a free information environment is associated with the name of the national leader Heydar Aliyev. Because Heydar Aliyev, as a leader well versed in world experience in this field, knew well that the information space, information resources and technologies of each country determine the level and dynamics of the socio-economic and cultural development of society. It was during his presidency that a purposeful policy was launched to ensure the formation and comprehensive development of free, independent, internationally competitive, democratic national mass media in the country. The Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, adopted in 1995, unequivocally established freedom of speech, thought and information, the right of everyone to receive and disseminate information, and the inadmissibility of any censorship over the media. Since the end of the 20th century, wide opportunities have been created in Azerbaijan to ensure freedom of speech and information, to form a democratic, pluralistic press, to establish its legal and normative basis, and to ensure its economic independence. By the Decree of the President of Azerbaijan dated August 6, 1998, the General Department for the Protection of State Secrets in the Press and Other Mass Media under the Cabinet of Ministers was abolished [3], putting an end to censorship once and for all. Other measures envisaged in the Decree ensured the development of independent mass media, and the freedom of speech, information and opinion of citizens as enshrined in international law and the Constitution of Azerbaijan. At the First Congress of Journalists of Azerbaijan in 2003, an independent Press Council was established, which performs the functions of a self-regulatory body of the press and regulation of relations between state bodies and the press.

It should be noted that the modern information security and security policy of Azerbaijan is ensured by legal, organizational-technical and economic methods. Here, legal methods mean the development and adoption of "normative legal acts regulating relations in the information sphere, normative methodological documents related to information security and security. Organizational-technical methods include the detection of technical devices, programs, etc. that pose a threat to

the normal functioning of information and telecommunication systems. Economic methods are related to the implementation of economic measures in the field of ensuring information security and security and their financing" [13, p.968].

In December 1999, the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Mass Media" was adopted in a new format [20]. According to experts, this new law fully guarantees all democratic requirements: freedom of speech and information, independence and free activity of mass media and journalists. In addition, in 2002, in cooperation with the Council of Europe, the Law "On Television and Radio Broadcasting" was developed and adopted, which fully meets international standards [31], in 2003, an institution was created - the National Television and Radio Council, which will ensure that activities in the field of electronic media are organized in accordance with democratic norms and is subject only to the law in its activities, and in 2004, a draft law "On Public Television and Radio Broadcasting" was developed and adopted [16].

It should be noted that the Council of Europe experts directly participated in the preparation of the law and most of the principle provisions were agreed upon with them. In addition, in 2004, the Law "On State Secrets" and in 2005, the Law "On Access to Information" were approved for the full realization of the freedom of journalists to receive information [15].

The preparation and adoption of the mentioned laws were very important steps in terms of the state policy of Azerbaijan in the information field. Thus, it is enough to show this fact alone that after the adoption of the Law "On Access to Information", the formation of public relations departments and press services began in state bodies. All information owners, central and local government bodies determined by the law, created their own Internet information resources and made them available to journalists. Currently, consistent measures are being taken to improve the activities of these resources.

After gaining independence, Azerbaijan, which has been experiencing its own period of development in all areas, has made successive decisions and signed relevant decrees and orders to ensure freedom of speech and information, strengthen the material and technical base of the media, and strengthen the social protection

of journalists. On January 9, 2003, by the Decree of the President of Azerbaijan, the debts of newspapers to the "Azerbaijan" publishing house were frozen for 3 years, and in March 2006, it was decided to pay their debt in the amount of 450 thousand US dollars from the state budget [13, p. 971]. It should be noted that since 2000, the anniversaries of the Azerbaijani national press have been celebrated at the state level and journalists are awarded honorary titles and state awards every year. Now, one-time financial assistance is allocated by the state to the country's leading newspaper editorial offices and information agencies every year. As a result of the continuous work carried out in this area, the "Concept of State Support for the Development of Mass Media in the Republic of Azerbaijan" was approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on July 30, 2008 [1]. The main goal of state support for the development of mass media is to develop freedom of thought, speech and information, taking into account the role of mass media in the process of building civil society, support the independence of mass media, improve the mechanism of assistance to editorial offices, stimulate the application of new information and communication technologies in the information sector, strengthen effective cooperation between society and mass media, create conditions for increasing the professionalism and responsibility of journalists, strengthen their social protection, and effectively use the potential of mass media in solving priority issues for the state and society. On April 3, 2009, in accordance with the requirements of the Concept, the State Support Fund for the Development of Mass Media was established under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan [2]. The main task of the Fund is to finance the implementation of the provisions of the Concept for the development of freedom of speech and information, mass media, as well as programs, projects and other events of the media. By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On measures to strengthen the social protection of Azerbaijani press workers" dated July 22, 2010, special funds were allocated for the construction of a residential building for journalists, and the opening ceremony of the building built for journalists was held on July 22, 2013. New apartments were distributed to 156 media workers, and on the same day, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan signed the Decree "On additional measures to strengthen the social protection of Azerbaijani press workers" and allocated funds for the construction of a new 240-apartment building for journalists. Thus, on July 22, 2017, the apartments specified in the decree were presented to journalists on the occasion of the "National Press Day". It should be emphasized that the development process in Azerbaijan, which has been evident in all areas since the years of independence, has not bypassed the electronic media sector, and new private television and radio channels have been opened. In recent years, the scale of cable television has expanded. Currently, 10 nationwide, 1 satellite, 14 regional and 14 cable televisions, and 14 radios operate in Azerbaijan. In 2005, the "Azerbaijan Television and Radio Broadcasting" Closed Joint-Stock Company was established on the basis of the Azerbaijan State Television. In the

same year, the Public Television and Radio Broadcasting Company was established and began its activities. All necessary measures have been taken to provide the material and technical support of Public Television and to actually start its activities.

At the same time, in accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated 2001, the introduction of digital broadcasting in the country began.

The information security policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan consists of the protection of state, public and individual information resources, as well as the implementation of a complex of measures aimed at protecting national interests in the information field. In order to ensure the security of our country in the information field, the national system and information infrastructure in the field of information protection, as well as state information resources, are being developed and strengthened in the country. In recent years, many important measures have been taken to develop information and communication technologies (ICT). The ICT sector, which is one of the priority areas of development in Azerbaijan, is entering a qualitatively new and high stage of development today [21]. The President of Azerbaijan has also approved the following important documents: "National Strategy on Information and Communication Technologies for the Development of Azerbaijan (2003-2012)", "State Program on the Development of Communication and Information Technologies in the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2005-2008", "State Program on the Creation and Development of the Space Industry in the Republic of Azerbaijan", etc. Within the framework of the strategy, the state programs "Electronic Azerbaijan - 2005-2008" and "Electronic Azerbaijan - 2010-2012" were adopted and implemented [35].

However, it should be noted that despite the serious work done in the field of national information security, Azerbaijan still lags behind the global level in many indicators. For this reason, the development of the information society in the country, communication and information technologies, as well as the full implementation of the tasks set by the "National Strategy for the Development of ICT" are considered one of the important tasks of the currently implemented state policy. Taking this into account, on April 2, 2014, the President of the country signed an Order on the approval of the "National Strategy for the Development of the Information Society in the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2014-2020". And thus, the second national action program was adopted in the country [33]. It should be noted that the previously adopted National Strategy covered the period 2003-2012 and defined the main tasks and directions of the national action program in this area, the main principles and priorities for its implementation.

The development of Internet media, the existence of freedom of thought and speech on the Internet, the widespread use of electronic newspapers and magazines, foreign and domestic social networks are new opportunities provided to society by ICT. According to the decree signed by the head of state, "The main goal of the National Strategy is the establishment of an information society in the country, the effective use of the

opportunities it creates for the development of citizens, society, and the state, the continuous and sustainable progress of the country, the comprehensive application of ICT in public administration, as well as its development as an economic sector that gives impetus to the development of socio-economic and cultural spheres” [37].

In the speech of the head of state on the mentioned legal document, it is noted that “The development of Internet media, the existence of freedom of thought and speech on the Internet, the widespread use of electronic newspapers and magazines, foreign and domestic social networks are new opportunities provided to society by ICT.

The above-mentioned issues, on the one hand, ensure freedom of speech and press, information in our country, and on the other hand, they condition the attitude and support of the media to the problem of information security of the state. At this point, there is a need for scientific analyses around the state's information policy and information security. The modern information society, the main strategic commodity of which is information, takes care of the preparation of relevant institutions and theoretical and conceptual documents in order to regulate existing and potential relations, as well as activities in this area. Such a necessity also causes the emergence of the state's information policy.

The state's information policy is understood as the regulatory activity of state bodies aimed at the development of the information sector. The information sector includes telecommunications, information systems and mass media (mass media), as well as the set of production and relations related to the creation, protection, processing, demonstration, and transmission of all types of information (business, entertainment, scientific-educational, news, etc.) [1].

Today, Azerbaijan is also trying to contribute to the strengthening of peace and security in the world, and is actively participating in inter-civilization dialogue initiatives.

In the modern era, the availability of objective, impartial, and honest information to people all over the world ultimately serves to strengthen peace and security on Earth, expand cooperation between countries and peoples, and expand dialogue between civilizations.

One of the issues covered by information policy in the field of mass media is ensuring information security, which is an integral part of national security. The bulletin “Support for the Promotion of State Policy in the Press” prepared by the League of Independent Journalists regarding the national security policy of the state indicates that although the national security policies of states differ from each other, they should cover at least three main issues: the role of the state in the international system, perceived local and international problems, situations, and the obligations that participating actors must fulfill in response to these problems and situations [26].

Before discussing information security, its role in the modern technogenic, civil, and information society, its concept, goals, and objectives, its role in the political

system, so to speak, multidisciplinary, inter-institutional, should be determined.

The purpose of information policy is to obtain an information system to ensure the information-psychological security of citizens and the country, to provide information-analytical support for state policy, and to reach the population with decisions and programs adopted by the state as the main subject of management.

Information war and information conflict also manifest themselves prominently in this context. In the implementation of all these processes and in achieving certain results, a great mission falls on the media. Because in the implementation of the above-mentioned processes, media outlets, as objects and subjects, perform important functions. First of all, because the manifestation of the state's information policy on a local, regional, global scale and the speed at which this occurs depend on the media. The media itself, by participating in this process, directly affects the form in which that policy is accepted by society. At the same time, the existence of cases of politicization of the media itself has already made it an integral part of politics.

The areas of national security - economic, political, military, border, etc. For external and internal threats, methods of their prevention are among the main issues in information security. True, the methods of ensuring their security differ from each other, which is why the laws we mentioned above alone could not be enough to ensure information security in Azerbaijan. That is why later many other issues - threats to the country's information security were reflected in a general and brief form in the National Security Concept and the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On National Security". The National Security Concept states that the information security policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan consists of the implementation of a complex of measures aimed at protecting state, public and individual information resources, as well as protecting national interests in the field of information. It is noted here that the national interests of the Republic of Azerbaijan consist of a set of political, economic, and social needs that ensure the fundamental values and goals of our people, the progress of man, society and the state, which are also reflected in the concept in the form of points [4]. As reflected in the concept, national interests include:

- protection of the independence and territorial integrity of the state, ensuring the inviolability of its internationally recognized borders;
- preservation of the unity of the Azerbaijani people, promotion of the idea of Azerbaijaniness;
- protection of the cultural and historical heritage and spiritual values of the Azerbaijani people, as well as enrichment with universal values, development of their language, self-awareness, patriotism and national pride, intellectual potential, etc. [6].

Information security policy, the main national interests of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the information sphere are classified in the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan “On National Security” in the following areas:

- ensuring the constitutional rights of citizens to legally obtain, transmit, prepare and disseminate information;
- protection and development of information resources;
- formation of the information space and ensuring its protection;
- entry into the world communication and information system [37].

Article 15 of the law lists economic, military, social, information, ecology, science, culture, spirituality and other areas as the main areas of national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan [41].

The main measures taken to ensure the national security of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the field of information are classified in the mentioned Law as follows:

- Creation and strengthening of a national system in the field of information protection, as well as state information resources in the Republic of Azerbaijan;
- Collection of objective and preventive information for the purpose of implementing information support for decision-making by state bodies and officials;
- Development of the information structure;
- Fight against crime in the field of computer information;
- Ensuring information security and freedom [24].

When considering the National Security Concept and the Law on National Security, we see that in both legal documents the problem of information security is not set as a primary task. In these documents, the problem is classified only against the background of the general national security of the country. International experience shows that it would be more expedient to create a separate Information Security Concept in this area in Azerbaijan. And against this background, it would be more effective in fulfilling the tasks set by the state in the field of information security and achieving concrete results.

"Society is worried, opportunists are at work, and official bodies are busy with more serious matters. The Armenian press, very agile and in several languages, spreads provocative information, trying to create confusion in both Armenian and Azerbaijani society... The fact that those who never followed the Armenian press said "Armenians wrote like this" or shared statuses about it, already showed that the enemies had made some progress in the information war. We do not know about the front, but the press front is before our eyes: Armenian information has gone on the offensive and is occupying our information space... In such a situation, our serious press, in the truest sense of the word, began to wage war very seriously. Almost everyone worked around the clock. There were two main directions here:

1. To study the situation on the front;
2. To prevent the enemy's information bombardment...

But this is not an easy task. Because the Azerbaijani press was not fighting the Armenians alone on this front. "The fight against Facebook "heroes" and oppor-

tunistic sites that spread disinformation and provocative rumors of the Armenian press to Azerbaijani society has also begun" [36].

It should be noted that the 44-day Patriotic War brought the issue of information security to the forefront. The society was once again made aware that war is not only fought with weapons, but also the importance of carrying out strong work in the field of information and information security. The easiest way to do this is, of course, the media. We would not be wrong to say that the media has been the most powerful propaganda weapon of all times. It is for this reason that, as in the whole world, the role of the media - television, radio, press, online and social media - in the information security policy pursued by Azerbaijan as a state, both locally and internationally, is great and undeniable.

We live in the information age, in the era of the development of the Internet and information technologies. More than 60 percent of the Azerbaijani population uses the Internet. True, this should be considered a gratifying fact. However, we must not forget that even the safest tool in the world can turn into a cold weapon when it is not in the right hands. In the information space, the Internet and information media are used not only to satisfy people's information needs, but also as a special means of sabotage. It is in this way that they conduct a slander campaign against individual nations, states and people.

As can be seen from the views of President Ilham Aliyev, the Concept of information security should separately reflect the main directions of the information policy to be implemented in connection with the Armenia-Azerbaijan, Nagorno-Karabakh conflict and the tasks ahead in this area. Let's take a look at the speech of the head of state: "Armenia is currently showing special zeal in the information war being waged against Azerbaijan. It must be admitted that the Armenian lobby is quite strong in Europe and other world countries, especially in large countries. They have been purposefully operating in this direction for decades, centuries, have been seriously organized, and have created a very aggressive and negative network. The driving force behind most of the negative information against Azerbaijan is the Armenian lobby. The Armenian diaspora tries to overshadow Azerbaijan's growing influence in the world and its successes in the political, economic, and cultural spheres in the media of various countries. The main goal of Armenians and the political circles that patronize them is to form a negative opinion about Azerbaijan in international public opinion at any cost" [20].

Protection of the information space of the Republic of Azerbaijan from modern threats is one of the main directions of national security. By his Order dated August 28, 2023, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan approved the "Strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Information Security and Cybersecurity for 2023-2027".

In a globalizing world, ensuring information security and cybersecurity has become a key issue both at the national and international levels. The main goal of this activity is to protect the interests of people, society

and the state. The practical activities carried out towards the formation and development of a national ecosystem in the field of cybersecurity have resulted in a significant improvement in the position of our country in international rankings. Azerbaijan has improved its position by 15 points in the “Global Cybersecurity Index 2020” (Global Cybersecurity Index, GCI) rating compiled by the International Telecommunication Union, ranking 40th among 194 countries with 89.31 points. “The Strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Information Security and Cybersecurity for 2023-2027” serves to increase the national level of information security to ensure the safe use of modern ICT by the state, society and people, to identify and implement measures to ensure the security of state and private networks, critical information infrastructures, as well as to create more favorable conditions for the protection of personal data, observance of human rights and freedoms enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The Strategy is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan and other normative legal acts, including the laws of the Republic of Azerbaijan “On National Security”, “On Information, Informatization and Information Protection”, the “Concept of National Security of the Republic of Azerbaijan” approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan No. 2198 dated May 23, 2007, as well as international agreements on information security to which the Republic of Azerbaijan is a party.

As can be seen, the successes achieved in the organization of new information activities in the Republic of Azerbaijan during the years of independence, freedom of thought, speech and information, have been an important part of the national state-building policy and the democratic achievements achieved. The Azerbaijani government is determined to continue fulfilling its responsibilities in the field of developing democracy.

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